

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.1.1: Intentional or unintentional introductions from the use of alien species in terrestrial and marine bioproduction systems

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Description

Section 3.3.1.1 assesses the role of intentional or unintentional introductions from the use of alien species in terrestrial and marine bioproduction systems as drivers of biological invasions. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

#1 TS=(((invesi* OR alien) OR feral OR exotic) AND species)

#2 TS=((intentional* OR unintentional* OR accidental*) AND introdu*)

#3 TS=(agricultur* OR forestr* OR fisher* OR aquacultur*)

#4 TS=review*

#1 AND #2

#1 AND #3

#1 AND #2 AND #3

#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

- **Searched time period:** 2000-2019

- **Date:** June 2020

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

#1 TS=(((invesi* OR alien) OR feral OR exotic) AND species), N=26,305

#2 TS=((intentional* OR unintentional* OR accidental*) AND introdu*), N=2,787

#3 TS=(agricultur* OR forestr* OR fisher* OR aquacultur*), N=421,539

#4 TS=review*, N=2,025,647

#1 AND #2, N=272

#1 AND #3, N=3,023

#1 AND #2 AND #3, N=159

#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4, N=99

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type (review) excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 2: Searched with above terms with timespan of 2000 to 2019, then excluded low relevant papers from Top 50 papers by experts' knowledge.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 34

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed: 133 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx